

A causal analysis of human mobility on colonization of disease-carrying tiger mosquitoes in Spain

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Abstract. The rapid expansion of the tiger mosquito (*Aedes albopictus*) in Spain poses an increasing public health risk for arbovirus outbreaks. This study uses the COVID-19 lockdown as a natural experiment to quantify the causal role of human mobility in mosquito colonization. To disentangle the effect of human travel from the confounding influences of physical proximity and climatic suitability, we apply double machine learning (DML). By partialling out these spatial and environmental factors, we found that when existing, stable human mobility flows transform into active risk corridors (because the origin municipality becomes invaded), the destination's baseline monthly risk of a first-time mosquito detection is multiplied by a factor of five. This constitutes a substantial surge in invasion hazard. These results provide the first empirical macro-level evidence of a causal link between human mobility and mosquito colonization.

Submission Type. Analysis; case study.

BoK Concepts. [AM9] Spatial regression and econometrics; [AM5-4] Spatial interaction.

Keywords. human mobility, citizen science, causal inference, tiger mosquito dispersal, Spain

1 Motivation and objective

The rapid expansion of the tiger mosquito (*Aedes albopictus*) across Spain poses an increasing risk of mosquito-borne diseases, such as dengue, chikungunya, and Zika. Local outbreaks are often triggered by imported cases in areas where these vectors are established (Aranda et al., 2006; Collantes et al., 2015). While traditional species distribution models incorporate environmental covariates and population density, they frequently neglect

dynamic human mobility, a potential driver of disease-vector dispersal (Kraemer et al., 2019; Barman et al., 2025). Micro-level evidence confirms mosquitoes hitch rides in cars (Eritja et al., 2017), enabling "leapfrogging" dispersal well beyond the natural invasion front. However, empirically disentangling the role of human mobility from physical distance remains a challenge due to their high structural correlation. Recent mechanistic models demonstrate that mobility data improve mosquito invasion predictions (Pardo-Araujo et al., 2026), but they rely on simulated counterfactuals. **This study leverages the unprecedented natural experiment of the COVID-19 pandemic—which temporarily decoupled mobility from geographic distance—to statistically quantify the causal effect of human mobility on tiger mosquito dispersal.**

2 Study design, data, and methods

2.1 Data construction

We constructed a comprehensive monthly panel dataset (2020–2024) covering the active mosquito season.

- **Biological target:** The outcome variable was a binary indicator representing the first-ever detection of the mosquito in a municipality during a given month (an absorbing state hazard). This was derived from harmonized entomological traps (Eritja et al., 2025) and *Mosquito Alert* citizen-science reports (Escobar and Mosquito Alert, 2023). Unlike entomological traps, citizen science provides continuous detection data and background tracking of participants, which we aggregated monthly as a measure of sampling effort to control for observer bias (Palmer et al., 2017).

- **Human mobility:** We used anonymized human mobility flows based on mobile network data from the Spanish Ministry of Transport (MITMS) (Ministerio de Transportes y Movilidad Sostenible (MITMS), 2024). To capture the potential for human-mediated transport of the mosquito, we calculated the rolling 3-month total of incoming trips originating exclusively from municipalities where the mosquito was previously detected.
- **Freight transport:** Recognizing that commercial logistics were explicitly excluded from the human mobility data, yet remain a potential mosquito dispersal pathway, we integrated synthetic European road freight flows from ETISplus (Speth et al., 2022) to capture dispersal via heavy goods vehicles.
- **Environmental controls:** Precipitation, temperature, and humidity were extracted from CERRA (Copernicus Regional Reanalysis for Europe) reanalysis (Copernicus Climate Change Service, 2021) to control for habitat suitability.

2.2 Modelling strategy: Double machine learning

Identifying causal effects in this context is challenged by the absence of a pure control group (a "no stayers" design (de Chaisemartin et al., 2024)), as every municipality experienced some mobility reduction. Furthermore, the risk of a mosquito invasion is highly heterogeneous, depending on complex, non-linear interactions between climate, demographics, and transportation networks. Standard linear models obscure these underlying biological dynamics and can yield systematically biased estimates.

To address this, we operationalize treatment exposure along two margins. The continuous *intensive margin* measures the raw volume of incoming traffic from invaded areas. The binary *extensive margin* evaluates initial integration into the mobility network, indicating whether a municipality receives incoming flows exceeding a designated high-traffic threshold. Crucially, transitioning into this *highly connected* state does not imply a sudden shift in human commuting behaviours. Instead, it reflects the spatial dynamics of the invasion itself. As the established *Aedes albopictus* population spreads, it eventually colonizes locations that already share intensive, historical human flows with uninvaded areas. Consequently, existing, stable travel networks simply transform into active risk corridors originating from the expanding invasion front.

We then employ a double/debiased machine learning (DML) framework (Chernozhukov et al., 2018). We use random forest models to estimate the conditional expectations of the mobility treatment and the probability of detection. The DML framework then applies two critical statistical corrections: *orthogonalization*, which ensures the final results are mathematically insensitive to minor prediction errors from the random forests, and *cross-fitting*, a data-splitting technique that prevents the models

from overfitting to noise. Together, these techniques allow us to non-parametrically partial out high-dimensional confounders (e.g., climatic suitability, population density, baseline freight logistics, overall sampling effort) and physical proximity to invaded areas, safely isolating the true vector dispersal dynamics without the biases typical of standard machine learning. We implemented the DML procedure using the `DoubleML` R package (?).

2.3 Data and Software Availability

Human mobility data were obtained from the Spanish Ministry of Transport (Ministerio de Transportes y Movilidad Sostenible (MITMS), 2024) using `spanishoddata` R package (Kotov et al., 2026). Tiger mosquito detection data were sourced from Mosquito Alert (Palmer et al., 2017) and entomological surveillance (Eritja et al., 2025). Synthetic freight data were derived from ETISplus (Speth et al., 2022). Socio-economic control data were obtained from the National Statistics Institute of Spain (INE, <https://www.ine.es/>). The code for the entire pipeline will be shared upon publication of this research project as a journal article.

3 Findings and results

Evaluating the extensive margin, we found that the transition into a highly connected state—where existing routes transform into active risk corridors—multiplied a municipality’s baseline risk of a first-time mosquito invasion by a factor of five. Over a typical nine-month mosquito season, this compounding hazard elevates a location’s cumulative invasion risk from approximately 1.2% to nearly 5.8%.

Subsequently, our intensive margin model evaluated the continuous effect of traffic volume to identify absolute tipping points. We observed that the invasion hazard surged continuously as incoming traffic from infested areas increased. Yet, this marginal effect saturated once volume reached approximately 1,000,000 trips over a 90-day period. Beyond this threshold, adding more vehicles did not meaningfully accelerate the timeline of establishment. Taken together, these findings provide empirical macro-level evidence that human mobility causally drives *Ae. albopictus* colonization.

Funding

Authors gratefully acknowledge the resources provided by the International Max Planck Research School for Population, Health and Data Science (IMPRS-PHDS).

This work used the Scientific Compute Cluster at GWDG, the joint data center of the Max Planck Society (MPG) and the University of Göttingen. In part funded by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG, German Research Foundation) – 405797229.

Declaration of Generative AI in writing

The authors declare that they have used Generative AI tools in the preparation of this manuscript. Specifically, the AI tools were utilized for language editing, improving grammar, and sentence structure, and LaTeX formatting, but not for generating scientific content, research data, or substantive conclusions. All intellectual and creative work, including the analysis and interpretation of data, is original and has been conducted by the authors without AI assistance.

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